

ASSESSING THE MARKET ABILITY OF VAPE PRODUCTS: AN ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF INFLUENTIAL FACTORS ON THE PURCHASING INTENTIONS TOWARDS VAPE PRODUCTS AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10570871>

ABSTRACT

In the Philippines, the use of vapes among 13 to 18-year-olds has become a concern, particularly for college students facing academic pressures and social influences. This study aims to dig into why college students decide to use vape products by examining their buying habits and the factors that influence their choices. Despite claims that vaping is safer than regular smoking, there's still uncertainty about its long-term effects. Young people, influenced by enticing marketing like flavored products and social media promotions, are increasingly drawn to e-cigarettes. The goal is to gain insights into what motivates these students. The Health Belief Model was used as the foundation for this investigation. The study surveyed a group of college students residing in Metro Manila, ranging in age from 18 to 26 years old. The survey was disseminated through Google Forms, and the results were analyzed using the data collected. According to the study findings, it became clear that, among the numerous factors examined, self-efficacy and cues-to-action stood out as the primary influencers significantly affecting the appeal of vape products in this particular demographic. These results offer valuable information for marketing professionals, policymakers, and educators aiming to understand and address the changing patterns of consumer behavior, especially concerning emerging products like vape items among the youth.

Keywords: *Vaping, vape usage, college students, purchasing intention*

INTRODUCTION

As the world evolves and progresses, the market is constantly bombarded with new products and trends. One of the emerging trends that has gained significant attention and controversy in recent years is the use of vape or electronic cigarettes. Vaping, as it is commonly known, is the act of inhaling and exhaling an aerosol produced by a vaping device. It is marketed as a safer alternative to traditional smoking, and its popularity has been rapidly rising among the younger generation, particularly Generation Z (Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health, 2022)

The prevalence of vaping amongst Generation Z has raised concerns and arguments over its marketability. This generation, born between 1997 and 2012, is noted for its technological prowess and high rate of social media usage. They also face specific obstacles due to growing up in a fast-paced and highly demanding world, such as the pressure to excel and continual dependency on technology and social media. Indeed, it is essential to note that while the use of e-cigarettes has been marketed as a safer alternative to traditional cigarettes, there is still a lack of concrete evidence on its long-term effects. Furthermore, the aggressive marketing strategies employed by e-cigarette companies, such as the use of flavors and social media influencers, have been attracting the younger population. The use of electronic cigarettes by high school students in the United States has increased from 1.5% in 2011 to 20.8% in 2018, according to a study conducted by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). In 2018 alone, there were an estimated 3.6 million high school and middle school vapers (Cullen et al., 2018). This is not just a US phenomenon; other nations, like the Philippines, are also seeing this pattern.

In the Philippines, however, vaping among Generation Z has gained significant traction due to the growing availability and appeal of vape devices. The 13 to 18-year-old age group had the highest prevalence of smoking or vaping among students aged 10 to 24 years old, with 11.7% and 16.3%, respectively, according to a survey done by the Department of Health and the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) in 2022–2023. (Baclig, C., 2023). The trend of vaping among Generation Z college students, specifically in the local community, has become a cause for concern, especially for their mental well-being. With the pressure and expectations of excelling in their chosen field, coupled with the influence of social media and peer pressure, the use of vape may pose potential consequences on their mental health.

The local literature provides a comprehensive overview of studies related to e-cigarette use in the Philippines, focusing on attitudes, behaviors, market trends, health effects, and the impact on mental well-being. Aljaberi and Yao (2021) emphasize the influence of positive attitudes and perceived behavioral control on e-cigarette use, urging healthcare professionals to investigate marketing strategies. Resano et al., (2023) highlight the widespread use of cigarettes and e-cigarettes among nursing students,

emphasizing the need for targeted anti-smoking and anti-vaping initiatives. Eijk et al. (2022) discuss the growing e-cigarette market in Southeast Asia, stressing the potential impact on public health and recommending preventive measures.

Sese and Guillermo's (2023) study explores the effects of vaping on stress levels among college students, revealing that vaping may not necessarily reduce stress and is sometimes used as a coping mechanism. Palmes et al. (2021) focus on adolescents' knowledge, perceptions, and behaviors toward vaping, providing insights into the adverse physical effects of vaping on health. Aljaberi and Yao's (2021) examination of the growth and marketability of vape products in the Philippines emphasizes factors contributing to the rise of vaping without specifically addressing its impact on mental well-being.

Marques et al. (2021) discuss smoking cessation support in the U.S., highlighting the potential of e-cigarettes as a tool but cautioning the need for further research. Tsai et al. (2018) reveal that vape shops serve as social venues for consumers, positively impacting mental well-being by fostering a sense of community and acceptance. Javed et al.'s (2022) survey suggests potential marketability of e-cigarettes among individuals with mental health conditions, though concerns about dependence are raised.

In foreign literature, Grande et al. (2022) find that vaping may contribute to stress management, but long-term effects include an increase in depressive symptoms. Mordor Intelligence (2018) links the popularity of e-cigarettes to perceived health benefits and relative affordability. Perry Dinardo (2019) notes the increasing popularity of vaping, emphasizing its potential harm for youth as a gateway to addiction. Nguyen and Mital (2022) discuss the popularity of e-cigarettes in schools, with conflicting results on anxiety disorder reduction.

Struik et al. (2020) examine vaping trends among North American youth, identifying a lack of awareness about negative effects but emphasizing the influence of perceived greatness and social media. Jha and Kraguljac (2021) assess peer and family influence on teen vaping, highlighting the perception of vaping as trendy and its positive impact on social status. Landry et al. (2019) explore vaping prevalence among U.S. college students, pointing out the increased likelihood of mental health disorders associated with vaping. Wang et al. (2020) indicate high awareness of e-cigarettes among university students but a low incidence of use, influenced by perceptions of reduced harm compared to traditional cigarettes.

Harrell et al. (2019) suggest short-term relaxation and decreased stress levels through vaping among young adults but emphasize the lack of long-term research on mental health effects. Cabral (2022) investigates associations between psychological distress, intentions to use e-cigarettes, and reasons for vaping among young adults, finding that vaping is perceived as a safer alternative but associated with higher levels of anxiety, depression, and stress.

Hence, this research aims to comprehensively analyze the marketability of vape products among college students, with a specific focus on identifying and understanding

the influential factors that impact purchasing intentions. The study aims to assess the influential factors, including perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, perceived self-efficacy, and perceived cues-to-action. Through demographic analysis and data collection, the research seeks to provide insights into the preferences and behaviors of college students towards vape products, ultimately contributing to a better understanding of the market dynamics in this demographic. The findings will benefit academic research and provide practical implications for businesses, stakeholders, and entrepreneurs involved in regulating and promoting vape products among college students.

Research Questions

Research Question no.1: What is the profile of respondents in terms of:

1. Age
2. Sex
3. Educational Status
4. Residence

Research Question no. 2: How often do they use vape products?

Research Question no. 3: Do the vape influential factors impact the respondents' purchase intention?

- 3.1 Is perceived susceptibility a significant predictor of vape purchase intention?
- 3.2 Is perceived severity a significant predictor of vape purchase intention?
- 3.3 Is perceived benefits a significant predictor of vape purchase intention?
- 3.4 Is perceived barriers a significant predictor of vape purchase intention?
- 3.5 Is perceived self-efficacy a significant predictor of vape purchase intention?
- 3.6 Is perceived cues to action a significant predictor of vape purchase intention?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design of the study was quantitative and descriptive, incorporating a predictive approach to analyze the impact of influential factors on purchasing intentions among college students for vape products. The data underwent analysis using descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis to identify the factors influencing purchasing intentions and to test the hypotheses of the study. The research design allowed the researchers to assess the marketability of vape products and offer recommendations for marketing strategies (Phonin, S. et. al. , 2018). The quantitative approach was adopted to collect systematic and quantifiable data from a representative sample of college students. This approach empowered the researchers to measure the prevalence of vaping behavior, pinpoint factors associated with vaping, and quantify the perceived impact of vaping usage on purchasing intentions. It had been utilized to discern trends

and averages, formulate hypotheses, scrutinize causality, and extrapolate findings to larger populations.

A non-experimental methodology had been implemented in the study, as the researchers refrained from manipulating or controlling any variables. This approach facilitated the collection of unbiased data on the actual behaviors, attitudes, and perceptions of college students regarding vaping. A structured questionnaire was given to gather quantitative data from college students. The study employed a survey method to collect data from a sample of college students who were either current or potential users of vape products. The survey measured the participants' attitudes, preferences, beliefs, and behaviors regarding vape products, along with their demographic characteristics.

Research Locale

To gather data for this study, an approach was employed, utilizing online survey methods. Online platforms, such as Facebook, Messenger, and Gmail, were leveraged to distribute survey links to potential participants, ensuring the convenience of responding from their preferred devices. This comprehensive approach aimed to maximize participation and ensure the collection of diverse perspectives from a representative sample of 100 college students within Metro Manila.

By employing online survey methods, the researchers were able to reach a wide range of Gen-Z college students and gather comprehensive data on their purchasing intentions regarding vape products. This multifaceted approach ensured the collection of diverse perspectives and enhanced the overall reliability of the study's findings.

Population and Sampling

The study targeted Gen Z college students aged 18 to 26. This demographic group, born between the mid-1990s and the early 2000s, comprises the Generation Z cohort, which is noted for its distinct qualities, attitudes, and behaviors, notably in the context of marketing and consumer preferences. (The Annie E. Casey Foundation, 2021)

The selection of Gen-Z students as the target demographic was driven by their unique purchasing and consumption patterns, which set them apart from previous generations. According to McKinsey & Company (2023), Generation Z is widely recognized as the most influential consumer group in the current market, making their insights particularly valuable in assessing the market potential of vape products.

A non-probability sampling methodology was used to conduct the research, with both purposive and convenience sample approaches used. The researchers were able to use the purposive sampling method to purposely pick participants based on certain criteria, guaranteeing that the responses were college students within the desired age

range. Furthermore, convenience sampling was adopted for practical reasons, making it easier to collect data from participants who were readily available and ready to participate.

The researchers hoped to provide a representative portrait of the Gen Z college student by applying purposive and convenience sampling. The optimal sample size for this study was determined using the G-Power formula a sample size of 100 respondents with a margin of error of 5% and a power of 95%

This method ensured that the study's findings applied to the study's target population of Gen Z college students, providing vital insights into their comprehension and opinions toward vape goods. The use of multiple sampling procedures, together with the application of the G-Power formula to calculate an acceptable sample size, resulted in a diverse and representative sample of participants, boosting the overall reliability and validity of the study's findings.

Research Instruments

The researchers used online platforms for survey data collection in which the college student uses a Google form to complete the survey questionnaire. The questionnaire focuses on gathering essential demographic information, including gender, educational status, age, residence, and vape frequency. This demographic profiling serves to segment and analyze the data based on individual characteristics, allowing for insights into variations in perceptions and experiences. Understanding these demographic factors provides an important context for interpreting vaping behavior and purchasing intentions across various population segments.

The questionnaire also assessed the extent and nature of respondents' vape product usage, measured respondents' intentions to engage in future vape product purchases, and investigated the underlying motivations or restrictions. In addition, the questionnaire assesses how respondents' perceptions and beliefs about factors influence their decisions about vape product purchases in relation to the variables. The research aims to gain a deeper understanding of the influential factors that influence vaping behavior and purchasing intentions by investigating these areas.

The research instrument used in this study was a self-made questionnaire that aimed to measure the respondents' perceptions of the topic under investigation. The questionnaire included multiple-choice questions that addressed several facets of the study topic. To confirm the instrument's validity and reliability, it underwent a comprehensive validation procedure conducted by field specialists. The instrument underwent content validity, which examined the items' relevance and comprehensiveness to the study's aims, as well as face validity, which evaluated the clarity and appropriateness of the language and instrument structure. The validators' input and suggestions were integrated into the final version of the questionnaire, which was pilot tested on a small sample of the target demographic before being sent to the larger sample.

Data Collection

Data collection for this research was primarily conducted through the administration of surveys and questionnaires. Surveys are a research method that involves asking individuals a series of questions to gather information about their opinions, beliefs, or experiences (Creswell, 2018). Questionnaires, on the other hand, are specific types of surveys that are designed to collect quantitative data, typically in the form of closed-ended questions (Koehler & Casey, 2021). The use of surveys and questionnaires was chosen for this research due to their accessibility, time efficiency, and ability to reach a large number of respondents. To facilitate convenient data collection, electronic or Google forms were employed. Google Forms was utilized for online data collection, which makes it convenient for both parties. This approach ensured that the research was accessible to a wider range of participants, maximizing the potential for comprehensive data collection.

RESULTS

Data Analysis

The following section of the paper includes the data gathered by the researchers from the survey through Google Forms. The data collected were properly presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The results of the findings determine whether the influential factors are an effective variable to influence the purchasing intentions of Gen Z college students within Metro Manila.

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Demographic			Frequency	Percentage
Age	Educational Status	Residence		
18-26	College Student	Metro Manila	100	100%

This study's respondents are 100 college students residing in Metro Manila. The chosen participants are from Generation Z (18-26 years old) who have used vape products for at least three months, which completed the 100% sample of this research study.

Table 2: Descriptives

Variables	Mean	SD
Perceived Susceptibility	3.61	.38
Perceived Severity	3.51	.41
Perceived Benefits	3.56	.37
Perceived Barriers	3.56	.38
Perceived Self-efficacy	3.62	.35
Perceived Cues-to-action	3.58	.37
Purchasing Intention	3.56	.41
TOTAL	3.57	.38

The presented table offers descriptive statistics concerning a collection of variables pertinent to a specific study or context. Each variable, encompassing Perceived Susceptibility, Perceived Severity, Perceived Benefits, Perceived Barriers, Perceived Self-efficacy, Perceived Cues-to-action, and Purchasing Intention, is assessed utilizing a 5-point scale. The frequency column denotes that there are 5 observations for each variable, except for Purchasing Intention, which has 6. The mean values exhibit a range from 3.51 to 3.62, indicating a moderate level of consensus or perception among respondents. The standard deviations, spanning from 0.35 to 0.41, suggest relatively limited variability in responses for each variable. With a total of 36 observations, the aggregate mean for all variables stands at 3.57, accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.38. These statistics furnish a succinct overview of the central tendency and distribution of perceptions and intentions within the scrutinized domain.

Table 3: Linear Regression

Table 3.1: Perceived Susceptibility

Variable	Pearson Correlation	P-value	Unstandardized Beta	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Perceived Susceptibility and Purchasing Intention	0.563	0.092	0.184	Accept H₀1: Perceived susceptibility is not a

significant predictor of vape purchase intention.

The table above shows how perceived susceptibility affects purchasing intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.092. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being accepted. As a result, perceived susceptibility is not a significant predictor of purchasing intention. There is also a positive moderately strong correlation (0.563) between the two variables, and each unit of perceived susceptibility has a 0.184 increase in purchasing intention.

Table 3.2: Perceived Severity

Variable	Pearson Correlation	P-value	Unstandardized Beta	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Perceived Severity and Purchasing Intention	0.566	0.143	0.152	Accept H₀2: Perceived Severity is not a significant predictor of vape purchase intention.

The table above shows how perceived severity affects purchasing intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.143. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being accepted. As a result, perceived severity is not a significant predictor of purchasing intention. There is also a positive moderately strong correlation (0.566) between the two variables, and each unit of perceived severity has a 0.152 increase in purchasing intention.

Table 3.3: Perceived Benefits

Variable	Pearson Correlation	P-value	Unstandardized Beta	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Perceived Benefits and Purchasing Intention	0.553	0.479	-0.102	Accept H₀3: Perceived Benefits is not a significant predictor of vape purchase intention.

The table above shows how perceived benefits affect purchasing intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.479. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being accepted. As a result, perceived benefit is not a significant predictor of purchasing intention. There is also a positive moderately strong correlation (0.553) between the two variables, and each unit of perceived benefits has a -0.102 decrease in purchasing intention.

Table 3.4: Perceived Barrier

Variable	Pearson Correlation	P-value	Unstandardized Beta	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Perceived Barrier and Purchasing Intention	0.543	0.406	0.104	Accept H₀4: Perceived Barrier is not a significant predictor of vape purchase intention.

The table above shows how perceived barriers affect purchasing intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.406. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being accepted. As a result, perceived barriers are not a significant predictor of purchasing intention. There is also a positive moderately strong correlation (0.543) between the two variables, and each unit of perceived barrier has a 0.104 increase in purchasing intention.

Table 3.5: Perceived Self-efficacy

Variable	Pearson Correlation	P-value	Unstandardized Beta	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Perceived Self-efficacy and Purchasing Intention	0.619	0.015	0.324	Reject H₀5: Perceived Self-efficacy is a significant predictor of vape purchase intention.

The table above shows how perceived self-efficacy affects purchasing intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.015. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater

than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, perceived self-efficacy is a significant predictor of purchasing intention. There is also a positive highly strong correlation (0.619) between the two variables, and each unit of perceived self-efficacy has a 0.324 increase in purchasing intention.

Table 3.6: Perceived Cues-to-action

Variable	Pearson Correlation	P-value	Unstandardized Beta	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Perceived Cues-to-action and Purchasing Intention	0.607	0.008	0.296	Reject H₀6: Perceived Cues-to-action is a significant predictor of vape purchase intention.

The table above shows how perceived cues-to-action affects purchasing intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.008. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, perceived cues-to-action is a significant predictor of purchasing intention. There is also a positive highly strong correlation (0.607) between the two variables, and each unit of perceived cues-to-action has a 0.296 increase in purchasing intention.

DISCUSSION

Understanding the factors that motivate people to buy e-cigarettes is essential for creating industry policies and public health initiatives that work. Two stand out as being significantly influential among several factors: perceived cues-to-action and self-efficacy. Customers who have a high level of self-efficacy have trust in their capacity to refrain from vaping even in the face of temptation. Peer pressure and persuasive marketing are resisted by this deep self-confidence. Individuals with low self-efficacy, on the other hand, experience vulnerability and are more prone to give in to social pressures or desires. Control and decision-making: Individuals who have a high self-efficacy regard themselves as having control over their vaping habits. This gives them the ability to make wise decisions and avoid rash purchases. In perceived cues to action, vape stores, ads, social media depictions, and even the presence of other vapers can operate as effective cues-to-action, provoking cravings and subconsciously prompting purchase decisions.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the research study delved into the intricate dynamics of factors influencing the purchasing intentions of college students in Metro Manila regarding vape products. The study assessed the influential factors, including perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, perceived self-efficacy, and perceived cues-to-action. Through a comprehensive analysis, it became evident that among the influential factors considered, self-efficacy and cues-to-action emerged as the key determinants significantly impacting the marketability of vape products within this demographic. The study highlights the importance of understanding the nuanced interplay between self-efficacy and cues-to-action. Through demographic analysis and data collection, the research seeks to provide insights into the preferences and behaviors of college students towards vape products, ultimately contributing to a better understanding of the market dynamics in this demographic. The findings will benefit academic research and provide practical implications for businesses, stakeholders, and entrepreneurs involved in regulating and promoting vape products among college students. and respond to the evolving landscape of consumer behavior, particularly in the context of emerging products such as vape items among the youth. As the vaping industry continues to grow and influence consumer choices, recognizing and harnessing the power of self-efficacy and cues-to-action is crucial for developing targeted interventions and marketing strategies that resonate with the preferences and intentions of college students in Metro Manila.

Recommendations

Recommendation Based on the Findings

Based on the conclusive findings of the research study on the marketability of vape products among college students in Metro Manila, strategic recommendations are offered for marketers and business owners aiming to optimize influential factors of self-efficacy and cues-to-action for the benefit of businesses and the economy at large. The pivotal role of self-efficacy in shaping purchasing intentions is recognized, making it imperative for marketers to develop targeted campaigns that enhance the perceived ability of college students to make informed choices regarding vape products. This may involve implementing educational initiatives, interactive content, or testimonials emphasizing the user's capacity to navigate the complexities of the vaping landscape. Furthermore, considering cues-to-action as another influential factor, the study suggests exploring innovative marketing approaches to prompt specific behaviors among college students. This could include strategically placed cues, such as peer testimonials, educational materials, or interactive experiences serving as triggers for informed decision-making. Moreover, given the unique context of vape product marketing, there is potential for differentiation through the incorporation of health and wellness elements, emphasizing

the positive impact of responsible usage. The implementation of such recommendations requires a nuanced understanding of the college demographic, ensuring that the messaging resonates authentically with their values and concerns. By adopting a proactive and differentiated approach based on self-efficacy and cues-to-action, marketers can potentially carve out a distinctive and ethically responsible niche within the college student market for vape products, one that aligns with the unique preferences and considerations of this demographic. In light of the research findings, the researchers proposed the launch of an educational campaign to dispel prevailing misconceptions surrounding vaping. The central objective is to challenge the perception that vapes are harmless and, instead, position them as a healthier alternative to traditional smoking. Emphasis is placed on highlighting the crucial role of individual responsibility in making informed decisions about vaping.

The recommended initiative takes a multifaceted approach, intending to make information on the comparative risks and benefits of vaping and traditional smoking easily accessible and engaging. An additional feature of the proposal involves advocating for a collaboration with the vape industry to enhance the campaign's credibility. This collaboration envisions the industry actively participating in implementing stringent quality control measures and contributing to ongoing research efforts. Concurrently, the campaign aims to present factual information in a dynamic, lively, and relatable manner to enhance its effectiveness.

The overarching goal of this collective effort extends beyond dispelling myths; it aims to cultivate a cultural shift towards responsible and informed vaping practices. By incorporating collaborative measures with an engaging and informative approach, the proposed blueprint sets the stage for a vibrant and informed vape revolution. The hope is that this comprehensive strategy will not only correct misconceptions but also establish a foundation for a more enlightened and responsible vaping landscape.

Recommendation for Future Research

For future researchers embarking on studies aligned with the research focus on the marketability of vape products among college students in Metro Manila, several recommendations emerge from our findings. Firstly, it is advisable to expand the scope of the study beyond the confines of Metro Manila, encompassing a broader geographical representation to capture diverse perspectives and variations in market dynamics. Additionally, increasing the sample size beyond our current 100 respondents could enhance the generalizability of the results. Moreover, future investigations should explore the temporal evolution of factors influencing purchasing intentions towards vape products, considering the dynamic nature of consumer preferences. To foster new knowledge and findings, researchers may delve into the socio-cultural, economic, and regulatory aspects shaping the vape industry, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted forces at play. Furthermore, incorporating qualitative research methods, such as in-depth interviews or focus group discussions, could offer richer insights into the intricacies of individual experiences and perceptions, complementing the quantitative data obtained in this study. These researchers' recommendations aim to guide future researchers in advancing our understanding of the intricate interplay between influencing factors and purchasing intentions regarding vape products among college students,

contributing to the evolving discourse on consumer behavior in this rapidly changing landscape. Finally, collaborating with academic institutions and public health organisations, create educational initiatives that provide youth and young adults the tools they need to withstand peer pressure and make well-informed decisions about vaping. These courses could be delivered as part of community outreach programmes or incorporated into curriculum at school.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

It was critical to adhere to ethical norms while measuring the impact of the research. This approach entailed evaluating research responsibly and conscientiously without causing harm to study participants or society as a whole. Ethical principles in research, as articulated by Baljinder Singh (2019), were a set of moral standards that directed researchers to carry out and communicate their research in an honest manner, with no intent to harm either the study participants or the broader community, whether this harm was deliberate or unintentional. Following ethical norms during the execution and presentation of research was critical for ensuring the study's credibility.

All participant information was kept secure and secret. The identity of participants was protected by providing them unique identification numbers. In any publications or presentations, the researchers did not provide any identifiable information about participants.

An informed consent form explaining the goal of the study, the procedures involved, and the risks and benefits of participation was given to all participants by providing the link for the questionnaire. The questionnaire were divided into parts, keeping the respondents to read the consent form before proceeding to the survey questionnaire.. Before taking part in the study, participants were given the opportunity to ask questions and were required to sign an informed consent form.

The researchers also considered the possibility of social stigma associated with vaping. The researchers made certain that participants were comfortable and respected throughout the study, and that their participation had no negative social consequences. The researchers ensured that the study was conducted in a responsible and ethical manner that protected the rights and dignity of all participants by adhering to these ethical principles.

Acknowledgments

First and foremost, we express our gratitude to the Almighty for the gifts bestowed upon us throughout our research journey, providing the perseverance and strength necessary to overcome the challenges encountered. Our confidence in Him significantly contributed to the advancement of this research.

A heartfelt appreciation goes to Ms. Marianne A. Iban, our research adviser, for her steadfast support, patience, inspiration, passion, and expertise. Her invaluable advice

guided us through the research process and paper drafting, teaching us the methodology and ensuring clear presentation of findings. Working under her guidance was a great privilege and honor.

Acknowledgments extend to our research team, whose time, patience, collaboration, and passionate support were integral to the study's success. Their willingness to contribute was crucial, and this study would not have been possible without their presence.

We express gratitude to our cherished families for their commitment, prayers, and sacrifices, fostering our education and preparing us for the future. Their continued spiritual support was instrumental in completing this study.

Appreciation is extended to the respondents, college students from Metro Manila, who volunteered their time to participate in our research surveys.

Lastly, we thank Our Lady of Fatima University for their assistance in conducting and concluding this research. Gratitude is extended to everyone who played a role, directly or indirectly, in supporting us throughout this research endeavor.

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SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Research Instrument and Likert Four-Point Scale Range Interpretation

POINT	SCALE RANGE	EXPLANATION
4	4.00 - 3.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.99 – 2.00	Agree
2	1.99 – 1.00	Disagree
1	1.00 – 0.99	Strongly Disagree

Questions	1	2	3	4
Perceived Susceptibility				
Using vape products reduces my chances of developing smoking-related health issues, which influences my purchase decisions.				
Using the belief of vaping as a safer alternative to smoking, I find myself drawn to vape products instead of traditional cigarettes.				
Using the belief that vape products are less addictive than tobacco, I am more likely to choose them when considering nicotine options.				
Using the concern about secondhand smoke's harm, I find myself favoring vape products to minimize the impact on others.				
Using the belief that vaping allows for greater control over nicotine intake influences my preference for vape products over traditional cigarettes.				
Perceived Severity				
I am certain that the severity of health concerns related to tobacco smoking encourages me to opt for vape products as a safer alternative.				
I am certain that the negative health implications of vaping did not affect my quality of life.				
I am certain that the negative health implications of vaping did not affect my academic performance.				
I am certain that the negative health implications of vaping will not affect my future employment prospects.				

I am certain that the severity of negative implications of vaping varies on the user.				
Perceived Benefits				
I prioritize the enjoyable aspects and social benefits of vaping over the perceived severity of health issues, influencing my decision to continue purchasing vape products.				
I am more likely to purchase vape products because I believe they can help me reduce stress and anxiety, contributing to an overall improvement in my well-being.				
The perceived cost-effectiveness of vape products is a significant factor influencing my decision to buy them.				
I find myself inclined to purchase vape products due to the convenience they provide in comparison to traditional smoking methods.				
I am more likely to buy vape products because of the perceived health benefits they offer.				
Perceived Self-efficacy				
Believing in my capacity to resist the potential negative effects of vape products motivates me to include them in my purchasing decisions.				
Believing in my ability to manage and control my use of vape products, positively influences my decision to purchase them.				
Believing in my capability to derive benefits from using vape products plays a crucial role in my decision to buy them.				
Believing in my ability to use vape products responsibly is a key factor in my decision to buy them.				
Believing myself proficient in using vape products fuels my confidence to purchase them.				
Perceived Barriers				
When barriers related to access, cost, or availability are low, I am more motivated to purchase vape products.				
I find myself more likely to buy vape products when I perceive them as socially acceptable among my peers				

The accessibility of reliable information about the ingredients and manufacturing process positively influences my decision to purchase vape products.				
There are limited alternatives to vaping that provide me satisfaction.				
Feeling stressed because of schoolwork makes it difficult for me to change my vaping habits.				
Perceived Cues-to-action				
Knowing that guidance or experts can support me in managing my vaping behavior, I feel more inclined to buy their products.				
Knowing the inclusion of trendy and popular flavors in vape products to be a compelling factor in my purchasing decision.				
Knowing the availability of informative advertisements and educational materials about vape products positively influences my decision to buy them.				
Knowing the positive recommendations from friends or peers about the effectiveness of vape products positively influences my decision to buy them.				
Knowing that vape products are easily accessible in various retail outlets positively influences my decision to buy them.				
Purchasing Intentions				
I am more likely to purchase vape products if I feel vulnerable to the consequences of using traditional tobacco products rather than the vape products.				
I am more likely to purchase vape product if I think the negative consequences of not using the product are severe.				
I am more likely to purchase vape products if I feel that the benefits of the vape products outweigh the costs involved.				
I am more likely to purchase vape products if I feel capable of managing any challenges associated with using the product.				
I am more likely to purchase vape products if the perceived barriers to purchasing the product are manageable.				

I am more likely to purchase vape products if there are external cues, such as advertisements or recommendations, that influence my intention to purchase the product.

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